

Construction, Deconstruction and Reconstruction in Translation: A Study of Translation from the Perspective of Bangladesh

**Dr. Elham Hossain,
Associate Professor,
Department of English,
Green University of Bangladesh,
Dhaka, Bangladesh.**

***Abstract:** Translation serves as a gateway to intercultural as well as multilingual understanding and apparently appears to be more than an inter- and intra-semantic transfer of the basic information. Jacques Derrida terms it much more complicated than merely a direct transfer of language. Transference of meaning from the source language to the target language engages both the linguistic and cultural processes. Lexical equivalence of words of one language to those of another language does not justifiably define translation. The most challenging task of translation is to grasp the arbitrariness of the meanings of the source language and incorporate them into the target language as much as possible. This arbitrariness creates spatiality which allows a translator to utilize his authority of imposing gravity, levity, faithfulness, or even faithlessness upon the target text. True, translation, in the present world of multilingualism, multiculturalism and globalization can be the gateway to reciprocation of cognition and mutual comprehensibility. However, it is also irrefutable that translation is never apolitical as it possesses the potential to construct, deconstruct and reconstruct the conscious incorporated into the source text. Besides, intertextuality between the ideology of the translator and that of the source text has the capacity to construct a new conscious and promote the hegemonic intention of the translator. Translatability is really a crucial issue pertinent to the translation process and requires in-depth research. In*

Bangladesh which is predominantly a monolingual country, translation from English to Bengali and vice-versa is widely practiced. This paper will address the research question— how translation process constructs, deconstructs and reconstructs in the situations of cultural untranslatability. It will also borrow Jacques Derrida's theoretical framework of translation theory and consider select Bangladeshi translators and their works for defending the research question.

Keywords: Deconstruction, Intertextuality, Multilingualism, Comprehensibility, Construction, Reconstruction

Translation, as Jacques Derrida thinks, is both possible and impossible. He further concedes that language, however intelligible, is not without equivocation, and thus, the translatability of any language provokes questions of authenticity, and arises suspicion about the dexterity of the translator in grasping the equivocal meanings of the source language and putting them into the target language. Derrida, in his essay, “What is a Relevant Translation?” declares, “As a matter of fact, I don’t believe that anything can ever be untranslatable or, moreover, translatable” (178). While translating a text two things are to be kept in mind- *property* and *quantity*. Jacques Derrida believes that a relevant translation must sustain these two things, that is, *property* and *quantity*.

Actually, “[T]ranslation is as much a creative activity as literature itself, and creativity is slave only to the dictates of the human mind, which knows no bounds” (Ramakrishna 87). Susan Gal calls translation “a very fruitful metaphor in anthropology” (226). Actually, translation is a semiotic process which involves both anthropological and ethnological matters pertinent to a community of people defined topographically as well as historically. It contributes to “the mobility and multiplicity of understanding” (Hossain 90). Inwardness with both the languages, that is, the source language and the target language enable a translator to comprehend the socio-political and cultural matrix engaged with the memory, associations and literary allusions of the texts. It is

aptly believed that “the worlding of poetics manifests as a mode of circulating and reading literary theory and criticism by transcending the boundaries of languages and cultures” (Lee 132). In this respect, a translator’s engagement with all these aspects enables him to bring about cultural transposition, essential to resonate the target text with liveliness and authenticity. It requires both synchronic and diachronic study of both the source text and the target text because there are chances to lose the aesthetic essence and affective engagement of the source text. Even Plato opposes translation as he believes that “it distorts reality while it translates things into verbal forms” (Das 10). Actually, translation is a move away from the original and at the same time an attempt of re-creating the original and thus it turns into a paradox to the consciousness of the target readers. It has the power of “transcending the boundaries of languages and cultures” (Lee 132). Again, translation is, by nature, a deconstructive process leading to the reconstruction of the source text to the target readers. Now in this process what is left out and what new is added to the target text are to be bridged together by the translators. Hence, the most difficult task of a translator is the bridging between these two. However difficult the task may be, it is a crying need for mutual comprehension, intertextuality of cultures and intersectionality of knowledge.

“Borrowing”, according to Dipesh Chakraborty, “is never a simple act of transfer; it always involves the grafting of new terms and concepts onto existing bodies of knowledge, transforming both” (xix). Translation is prone to domesticating alterity which emerges out of the problem of difference. This ‘difference’ is not transparent, but “the injurious and elusive *differance*, with an *a*, as introduced by Derrida (1976), meaning difference coming out of that which already is, but something that once manifested is renewed into something else- that is, difference as something that generates difference” (Maranhao xvi). True, identifications and differentiations come simultaneously. When a source text is translated into the language of the target readers, it goes through a paradigm shift of what the author means. The meanings of the

translated text are decided by the target readers and secondary meanings are constructed. Hence, Judaism opposes translation of its scriptures. Monotheism also advocates in favor of the untranslatability of its scriptures. In monotheistic religions recitation, memorization even without having the slightest cognition of the knowledge incorporated in it exactly are not discouraged because there prevails apprehension that translation may distort the exact meaning of the scriptures. Translation is a deconstruction process and it leads to reconstruction and as monotheism does not usually accept it, hence, translation is not promoted in it.

True, translation is an ever flourishing field in Bangladesh at present due to its constant exposure to the outer world and interaction and response to the present globalizing situations of the world. Nearly twenty million Bangladeshis live in different countries of the world as diaspora and immigrants. Due to the development of cyber technology, they can maintain communication with their home country. This phenomenal connectivity between the home country and the host countries serves as one of the stimuli in translation of foreign texts of various genres into Bengali for the Bangladeshi readership. Knowing each other is like conquering each other and this instinctive aspect significantly encourages translation. Many Bangladeshis living in different countries translate the local texts into Bengali and vice versa. For example, Anisuz Zaman who lives in Mexico has translated Juan Rulfo's *Pedro Paramo* into Bengali. He is also translating Bengali literature texts into Spanish language for the local readers of Mexico and thus bringing about intertextuality.

In this way, the maxim 'know and let know' gears up the task of translation. There are a huge number of classics in Bengali literature but it is a matter of regret that most of them are not yet translated into English for the international readership. At present some academicians, though a very good number of non-academicians are doing tremendously excellent job of translation, have come forward and made significant contributions to this field,

especially translation from Bengali to English, but in comparison with a considerably huge bulk of Bengali classics, the quantity of translations is not very remarkable. On the other hand, translation from English to Bengali is hugely much more than that from Bengali to English. There are a good number of translators who have already translated a huge number of classics from the world literature for the Bangladeshi readership. Khaliqzaman Elias, G. H. Habib, Kajal Bandyopadhyay, Mashrur Arefin, Razu Aluddin, Anis Uz Zaman, Elham Hossain and many others have translated a considerable number of classics of the world literature, myths, history, aesthetics and philosophy and thus they contribute to the development of intercultural reality. These are immensely contributing to the intertextualization between Bengali literature and the world literature.

True, translation, like all other branches of the modern epistemic life, is a business-oriented task. In Bangladesh, because of the lack of a central translation policy and the negative perception of the readers about translators, it is difficult to work in an organized way with creative impetus and consistency. Translators depend on the publishers and the publishers depend on the market in terms of the number of readers. Patronization or incentive from the government is not noteworthy. So, very often to cater to the demand of the publishers, a translator has to choose a text that may be widely received by the reading public. It, on the one hand, tells upon both the quality and on the other, it affects the quantity of transition. For the same purpose, best sellers get more concentration than best books. Again, because of a small number of English reading public, not more than 12%, translation from Bengali to English is not always economically encouraged. Besides, Bangladeshized English is not always accepted by the international publishers due to its lack of expected international standard. It is true that many countries have successfully domesticated English. India has Indianized English powerfully and this English is internationally accepted. Even Africa has Africanized English which is widely accepted by the English readers. The debate whether English should be read as a second language or a foreign language is not

still settled, and it considerably acts, like many other factors, as a block to the way of translation from Bengali to English.

Furthermore, Bangladesh is mostly a monolingual country though a good number of ethnic groups of people live here in the hill tracts and in some areas of the plain land with their own individual cultural and linguistic identity. But their languages and cultural norms do not enjoy a remarkable space in the main stream culture and language of the country. Besides, the interaction, intermingling and mutual social, political and cultural engagement between the mainstream population which is mostly Muslim and the ethnic people speaking and following ethnic languages and belief system is not remarkable at all. Ethnic people live in the periphery being isolated from the main stream population. There might have been a bridge language, may be English, between these two groups if their mutual interaction could have been ensured. Besides, nationalistic vanity emerged out of the consciousness of the people of Bangladesh about their 1952 Language Movement. Language was attempted to be weaponized by the then Pakistani rulers to re-colonize the people of the then East Pakistan and consequently, the people here then started a movement which led them to liberty in 1971. Hence, a kind of rooted resentment towards Urdu becomes an inevitable part of the minds of the Bangladeshis. Above all, this linguistic chauvinism also triggered hatred for English language of the colonizers who exploited Indian Subcontinent for 190 years. The Muslims responded to English and Urdu bitterly because of the resentment emanated from the fact that the English colonizers snatched away political sovereignty from the Mughals, who were mostly Muslims. After 1947 Muslims were geographically segregated from the Hindus and in 1971 this segregation was expedited through the emergence of the linguistic nationalism which regrettably very soon turned into Islamic nationalism because of the politicization of Islam by the then power-structures. It fortifies the wide perception that Arabic will be the language of the world after death and on the other, English is the language of the infidels. Such mindset among a vast majority of people of the country also retards considerable development of English

language. Not only that, English language remains confined within a particular class which is economically capable of affording quality education, to be distinct, English medium education for their children. Compartmentalization of education system into various streams acts as a block to the development of translation, especially from English to Bengali and vice-versa as a prolific field even though a good number of quality translation works have been done in Bangladesh since its political birth in 1971.

Fakrul Alam, a prominent translator of Bangladesh has translated a good number of books from Bengali to English, such as *Asamapta Atmajibani* (Unfinished Memoire of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman), *Amar Dekha Noya Chin* (China as I saw), *Bishad Sindhu* by Mir Mosharraf Hossain, *Essential Tagore*, *Poems of Jivananda Das* etc. All his translations are done with a view to taking Bengali literature in close contact with international readership. Nurul Huda's translation of Humayun Ahmed's *Nandito Naroke* (originally *In Blissful Hell*), is considered to be a seminal translation. Syed Waliullah's translation of his *Lalsalua Tree without Roots* is a seminal book for the international readership. Besides, Jasim Uddin's *Nakshikanthar Mathis* also translated into English for the wide range of international readership.

On the other, World literature translated from English to Bengali occupies an important place in the academia of Bangladesh. Khalikuzzaman Elias, a prize-winning translator, has translated a huge number of world classics that have brought about intertextuality among different streams of literary works, philosophy and Mythologies. He has translated from the works of Gabriel Garcia Marquez, such as *Peyarar Subash* (originally *The Fragrance of Guava*), Nikos Kazantzakis's *Zobra the Greek*, Joseph Campbel *Mither Shokti* (originally *Power of Myth*), Jonathan Swift's *Gulivarer Saforname* (originally *Gulliver's Travels*), Chinua Achebe's *Debotar Dhonurban* (originally *Arrow of God*), *Jonotar Lok* (originally *Man of the People*), Richard Wright's *Kalo Chele* (originally *Black Boy*), James George Frazer's *Manusher Zadubis was a Dhormachar* (originally *Golden*

Bough) and several other books of immense popularity and importance.

Khalikuzzaman Elias has translated *The Golden Bough* by James George Frazer into Bengali (vols. 1, and 2). The comparative study of mythology and religion which is offered by this book is very excellently brought down to Bengali readership. The impact of this translation on the overall condition of translation in Bangladesh is substantial. It is also a breakthrough of the tradition of translating mostly the bestsellers from the genre of literature in Bangladesh. Besides, translation of such a voluminous book seems to be like touching the peak of Everest in this field. Consequently, a trend of translating unabridged books was geared up in Bangladesh. Initially, many world classics were translated in abridge form for the adolescent readers. But Khalikuzzaman Elias caused a paradigm shift in the field of translation by opening up a horizon to the world classics to the Bangladeshi readership. Besides, through translation a significant scope of intertextuality occurs between the traditional myths, belief-system and pantheon and the Western epistemology. As a result, his translation caters to the interest of the Bangladeshi readership in the world literature, myths, religions and ethnography.

Elias' translation of *Nikos Kazantzakis*, a Greek writer, journalist, politician, poet and philosopher also opens up a new horizon where the Bengali readership finds true gems of the Greek epistemology which after being intersectionalized enriches Bangladeshi world-view and the poetics. Besides, his translation of Gabriel Garcia Marquez's work contributes to bringing Bengali readership in contact with Latin American authors with all its probable fragrance and taste. It is possible because he keeps every peculiar quality of the original intact. Readers widely appreciate Elias' translation and even they claim that Elias's translation does not appear to be translation at all while reading owing to the lucidity of his language. It occurs due to his command of both the source languages and the target language and his extensive knowledge of the situations and realities out of which the source text emerges.

Besides, he faithfully maintains to inform his readers what the author says, but not what the author means, and thus he effectively avoids manipulation of the target text with his subjectivity. His fair command of the cultural history and the diachronous location of the source text and the synchronous status and cultural location of the target text makes his translation a tremendous success. For example, he has used Bengali word *Debotar Dhonurban* in place of *Arrow of God*, the title of Chinua Achebe's one of the five seminal novel. The connotation produced by the Bengali term effectively takes the readers very close to the spiritual gravity of the Igbo community, which is one of the major themes of this novel.

But every reading is misreading because it is manipulated by the intuition and impulses of the readers. Every text, according to the New-critics, is autonomous and "since no two readings are identical, no translation can claim to have perceived the author's meanings completely and accurately" (Das 22). Hence, a translator's task is not to bother about the connotations and meanings of a text because unless the voice and tone of the source text are kept intact, translation must not be faithful and in such case, it has the apprehension of turning into a political weapon. He should rather convert the language only. But when translation becomes an apparatus to reform a society it borrows the subjective voice and tone of the translator as it occurred in the case of the translation of the great epic *Ramayana* from Sanskrit to Bengali during the medieval period by Krithivasa Ojah. Rama, the Khyatrya protagonist of the epic, in Bengali version is no more as much heroic as he is in the original Sanskrit *Ramayana* by Vhalniki. Krithivasa Ojah translated this epic during the 15th century when the Bengali society was shuddering with political and cultural transition due to the advent of Islam. It was also split up or compartmentalized into different castes. Feudal power-structure also divided the society into center and margin on the basis of economic and political capability. Bengalis are still renowned for their affective nature and empathy. They are comparatively soft-hearted and mostly fond of domestic life. They

try to avoid war or bloodshed. It happens because they are not usually *Khaytrya*. This *non-Khaytrya* disposition has embraced Rama and brought about a significant transformation in his attire and attitude. Rama, in Krithivas Ojha's translation, is different from that of Valmiki's *Ramayana*. Dr. Dilip Majumder, in his essay "Bangla Anubad Kabbyo: Kobi Krittivas" asserts that the *Ramayan* is recreated by the medieval poet Krittivas, saturated with his own impulses, distinct mode of presentation, gravity, levity and humor (113). Thus, translation receives from and responds to the time and the ethnographic realities of a period and deserves both diachronic and synchronic status. It is also the reason for which this translated version of *Ramayana* received a wide acceptance among the medieval Bengali readership. This may be termed as assimilation process of translation, essential to reproduce and reconstruct the source text. Khalikuzzaman Elias in a good number of his translations of the short stories of Chinua Achebe has put the local vernacular into the lips of some characters while translating their elocutions speaking native dialect. This adaptation of the local dialect makes a translation popular, but it cannibalizes the source text as it breaks down its diachronic attachment with its time and location.

Similarly, Fakrul Alam's translation of Jibananda Das's poems from Bengali to English carries the magnificence of his excellent scholarship. But his translation has, to some extent, missed the emotional attachment quite naturally with Bengal's soil, and it is quite an inevitable fate of any poem when it is translated from the source language to the target language, and this is probably the reason for which Robert Frost claims whatever is lost in translation is poetry. For example, Jivanananda Das's poem "Banglar Mukh Ami Dekhiachi" (translated version: "I Have Seen Bengal's Face") and Fakrul Alam's translation are put side by side for the better comprehensibility of the difference between the source text and the target text:

বাংলার মুখ- জীবনানন্দ দাশ

বাংলার মুখ আমি দেখিয়াছি, তাই আমি পৃথিবীর
রূপ
খুঁজিতে যাই না আর : অন্ধকারে জেগে উঠে
ডুমুরের গাছে
চেয়ে দেখি ছাতার মতো বড় পাতাটির নিচে বসে
আছে
ভোরের দয়েলপাখি – চারিদিকে চেয়ে দেখি
পল্লবের স্তূপ
জাম-বট-কাঁঠালের-হিজলের-অশথের করে আছে
চুপ;
ফনীমনসার ঝোপে শটবনে তাহাদের ছায়া
পড়িয়াছে;
মধুকর ডিঙা থেকে না জানি সে কবে চাঁদ
চম্পার কাছে
এমনই হিজল-বট-তমালের নীল ছায়া বাংলার
অপরূপ রূপ

দেখেছিল; বেহলাও একদিন গাঙুড়ের জলে ভেলা
নিয়ে –
কৃষ্ণা-দ্বাদশীর জোংলা যখন মরিয়া গেছে নদীর
চড়ায় –
সোনালি ধানের পাশে অসংখ্য অশ্বখ বট
দেখেছিল, হয়,
শ্যামার নরম গান শুনেছিল – একদিন অমরায়
গিয়ে
ছিল খঞ্জনার মতো যখন সে নেচেছিল ইন্দ্রের
সভায়
বাংলার নদ-নদী-ভাঁটফুল ঘুঙুরের মতো তার

I Have Seen Bengal's Face

Translated by
Fakrul Alam

*Because I have
seen Bengal's
face I will seek
no more;*

*The world has
not anything
more beautiful
to show me.*

*Waking up in
darkness,
gazing at the
fig-tree, I
behold*

*Dawn's
swallows
roosting under
huge umbrella-
like leaves. I
look around me*

*And discover a
leafy dome-
Jam, Kanthal,
Bat, Hijol and
Aswatha trees-*

কেঁদেছিল পায়।

*All in a hush,
shadowing
clumps of
cactus and
zedoary
bushes.*

*When long,
long ago,
Chand came in
his
honeycombed
boat*

*To a blue
Hijal, Bat and
Tamal shade
near the
Champa, he
too sighted*

*Bengal's
incomparable
beauty.*

*One day, alas.
In the Ganguri,*

*On a raft, as
the waning
moon sank on
the river's*

sandbanks,

*Behula too saw
countless
aswaths bats
besides golden
rice fields*

*And heard the
thrush's soft
song. One day,
arriving in
Amara,*

*Where gods
held court,
when she
danced like a
desolate
wagtail,*

*Bengal's
rivers, fields,
flowers, wailed
like strings of
bells on her
feet.*

True, translation deconstructs and reconstructs, and it happens in the case of Jivananda Das. It is found that translated text is quite different from the source text. This is, in Walter Benjamin's words, the liberation of the essence of meaning from the barrier of language. Even Rabindranath's translated version of *Gitanjali* is called by many a different book of poetry, not an exact translation of *Gitanjali*. This is invariably a common fate of a poem in

translation. However, Fakrul Alam's translation of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman's *Osamapta Atmajiboni* (translated as *Unfinished Prison Memoire*) and *Amar Dekha Naya Chin* (translated as *The New China as I Saw*) has uncovered a new horizon of our valuable history which remained neglected for many decades. Thus, translation has the power to re-invigorate history. Again, the task of translation has been attached with national awareness. Not only that, but also it contributes to the process of nation building in the way that it works as a bridge between our country and the rest of the world and thus ensures intertextuality, intersectionality and hybridization of cultures. In the world of borderlessness knowing one another is not a fashion, but a necessity and translation may work as a gateway to self-knowledge, and at the same time the knowledge about others.

Further, translation is not politically innocent and it involves a very strong economic aspect. These two aspects may misguide translation and thus give wrong shape to the perceptions of the reading public. During 1980s and 1990s, many classics of English and Russian literatures were translated in abridged form for the adolescents. Maxim Gorky, Tolstoy, Emile Bronte, Jonathan Swift, Edger Rice Burroughs and many other greats' works were translated into Bengali. Even the missionaries once distributed Bengali translated copies of the Bible among the people, especially in the rural areas with a view to proselytizing them into Christian. Besides, the translated classics like *Wuthering Heights*, *Gulliver's Travels*, *Tarzan* created a fantasy world regarding the countries of the whites who are rich and wealthy while we are the people of an impoverished country dreaming of becoming like them, actually Macaulay's mimic man. Besides a fantasy regarding the white men was constructed as they were depicted as the masters and the people from tropical countries were thrown into the binary opposition as their slaves. The reading of these translations also sowed the seed of brain drain in the form of imagination of the adolescents who dreamt of migrating to the white men's country to be like them. But at the same time, translation helped the people to enrich themselves and their writing by developing an acquaintance

with the wealth of knowledge of Europe and America and inspired intersectionality of knowledge and ideas. For example, due to the impact of such translations the genre of science fiction developed in Bangladesh.

With the onset of the twenty first century, due to the tremendous impact of globalization, corporatization of economy and cultural fluidity, translation becomes phenomenally widespread. But it has got some crucial aspects which deserve intensive critiques. Due to the industrialization and corporatization of the publication business, translators put more emphasis on translating the bestselling books than translating the world classics. Due to the immense impact of cyber technology, mode of reading changes drastically. Reading pdf or eBook has become a fashion and to some extent necessity of the day. Commercialization of education system has brought about a drastic change in the reading habit of the young readers. Besides, study is defined and determined in terms of the requirements of the job market. The mission of the corporate economy to produce intellectual slaves contributes to the construction of the taste of the reading public. Hence, due to the impact of all these phenomenal factors, in the third decade of the 21st century the perception of the translation-readers is shaped in such a way that they have started thinking that bestselling books are the best books of the time. It occurs due to the advertising and promotional politics of the publishers. But it is true that bestselling books and the classics are not same. Classics have a common trend of acquainting the readers with the tradition and cultural essentialism which in the multicultural era is constantly challenged. Reading bestselling books makes a man multicultural and prepared for the present-day market demands- is a common trend of the time. At present, it is deliberately alienating the readers from the classics to a great extent. At the same time, it is only serving the purpose of the corporate publishers.

Another trend of translation is found now. Only the prize-winning books and authors usually get almost hundred percent attentions for translation. In terms of this tendency, translators here are of

two categories. One category of translators is usually aged and they are mostly academicians. They are prone to translating classics, myths, histories, philosophies, literary and political theories and many other branches of epistemology. And other group of translators which is mostly constituted by comparatively young people is fond of translating bestsellers and prize-winning books. It marks the cleavage in our reading which two different generations receive differently.

Another crucial phenomenon emerges in the field of translation and it adds a new dimension to its existing spectrum. Especially after 2000 AD some universities in the country have introduced courses on 'Translation Studies'. Hence, a group of young people with theoretical knowledge are working with translation. They are translating some classic writings from postcolonial literature and theories. An intrinsic emergence of national awareness and interest in the past history of the nation motivate them to approach post-colonial theorists such as, Frantz Fanon, Aime Cesaire, Ngugi wa Thiong'o, Gayatri Chakraborti Spivak, Edward Said, Louis Althusser, Michael Foucault, Homi Bhabha and many others. Literary theories are also being translated into Bengali, but while reading them an acute scarcity of appropriate terms and terminologies makes the readers suffer. Sometimes, Bengali terms and terminology in translation sound more complicated than the original ones in English or French. But it is really encouraging for the Bangladeshi readership. The impetus that they show in translating from English to Bengali, is not exhibited in translating from Bengali to English. Thus, Bengali writings, though there are many classics, are getting marginalized. Translation must be done on both sides. Otherwise, it will not bring much benefit.

In Bangladesh, even today translators are not duly recognized or given remarkable institutional incentive. It is also widely but wrongly believed that translators are not creative authors. In terms of the translators' recognition on the part of the state is negligible, too. Bangla Academy gives a prize in the category of translation every year. There are some non-government organizations which

organize congregation of the translators at their own cost. They do not get much patronization from the government. Even publishers' attitude is discouraging and tends to push off the translators out of the mainstream creative authors because of its tenuous economic benefit. They keep translations "low because such books are financially risky" (Venuti 124). In maximum cases they are not ready to pay for buying copyright, Venuti opines:

Since the 1970s, furthermore, the drive to invest in bestsellers has become so prevalent as to focus the publisher's attention on foreign texts that were commercially successful in their native cultures, allowing the editorial and translating process be guided by the hope of a similar performance in different process to be guided by the hope of a similar performance in a different language and culture. (124)

Again, translation usually targets the domestic readership. As per the demands of the publishers, bestsellers are given priority for translation with a view to ensuring financial profit. Actually, best sellers address the concern of the majority of the population, they have wide market. This market-oriented translation has the risk of domesticating a foreign text and the moral, religious and political values out of which the source texts emerge. Thus, bestsellers in translation turn into a site or space where there are chances of the proliferation of values that may create a situation which leads the readers to the self-effacement. It happens because bestsellers have a tendency to blur "the distinction between art and life by sharing a specific discourse" (Venuti 126). This tendency is expedited when translation turns into a political apparatus to transform the target readers into 'Others'.

In line with this insight, it can be affirmed, as Venuti mentions, that even colonization in America, Asia and Africa was impossible "without the translation of effective texts, religious, legal, educational" (158). Even during the postcolonial period, neo-colonization process is going on hand in hand with "a vast array of translations, ranging from commercial contracts, instruction

manuals, and advertising copy to popular novels, children's books, and film sound tracks" (Venuti 158). Thus, translation has also a transnational role accompanied by the hegemonic countries' deliberate mission of building native-language audiences for their cultural products. True, translation works as an instrument of homogenization through its domesticating process. It also contributes to the transnational corporation hand in hand with imperializing mission since the end of the Second World War.

However, not only in Bangladesh but also all over the world, translation is still wrestling recklessly to guarantee its own future. But at the same time, it has been linked to the aspects such as, otherness, ideology, manipulation, power and neo-colonization. It has become a viably independent research area. In Bangladesh translation especially from English to Bangla is still at its adolescence and from Bengali to English is at its infancy. For organizing translation and leading it to maturity, it requires direct patronization from the state. Besides, self-translation may be encouraged, even though translation in this area is scarcely found. Actually, it refers to "the translation of an original work into another language by the author himself" (Santoyo 22). Kenyan author Ngugi wa Thiong'o at first writes in Gikuyu and then he translates it into English for the international readership. In this way he has created the written form of Gikuyu language, discovered its strength and taken it to a significant height. In this process of self-translation both the source language and the target language become enriched in mutual correspondences. As the author himself is the translator, he can grasp both the tone and voice of his expression. In Bangladesh there are a handful of authors who write in Bengali but their academic background is English literature and language. For example, prominent litterateur Syed Manzoorul Islam writes in Bengali. Rashid Askari and Samsad Mortuza write in English. And many other writers are well-versed in both the languages, that is, English and Bengali. Self-translation, in this connection, may contribute immensely to the spread of Bangladeshi literature throughout the world.

True, translation is not a philological job alone and “translating can never be linked to linguistics alone” (Lefevere 5). Extra-linguistic factors are involved in the translation process and in this vein, translation is a New-historicist process as it encapsulates all the factors related to both the periods of the source text and the target text. Translated text should attain the eligibility to be accepted by the target culture. It is a difficult but possible job and the translator’s capability to negotiate between the source culture and the target culture can help the translated text be acknowledged by the target culture. But this job must be done in the non-Eurocentric theoretical framework lest the target text might have chances to lose affinity with the source text. Like Cannibalism Translation Theory an indigenous translation theory may be developed which may enable the translators to “... gain creative power by “eating” the original text, just as the Tupinambas can gain physical or (and) spiritual strength after “eating” and thus translation turns into an empowering act as it enables the translators to digest the source text and create a new one (Jiang et al. 119). And here lies an important factor which deserves special consideration. If the translator does not have specialization in this field, he may be proved a failure ultimately. Only linguistic expertise cannot enable a translator to overcome this barrier on the way to comprehend the source text in its fullest meaning. Any translator of a literary text may be a man of literature. It does not guarantee that he should have a formal degree from a university in the certain field. It puts emphasis on his genuine inclination to the certain field in which he intends to do the job of translation. With a scientific mindset, if a person approaches a text of literature, then his translation may not smell literary. The mindset of the translator must match the field in which he decides to re-produce and re-create new texts out of the source texts. Otherwise, his work may lose its essential voice, tone and strength.

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